

**BASIC RESEARCH METHODS IN TUBERCULOSIS
PREVENTION AND TREATMENT**

Yitmasova Tuhfa Davlatovna

Assistant of the Department of Phthisiology and
Pulmonology of the Bukhara State Medical Institute
named after Abu Ali ibn Sina

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7188839>

Summary: This thesis is devoted to the most pressing issues of diagnosis and treatment of tuberculosis

Keywords: tuberculosis, diagnosis, treatment, drug resistance of mycobacteria .

Introduction: Currently, much attention is paid to the study of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, when *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is resistant to at least isoniazid and rifampicin. A high level of MDR -tuberculosis has a significant impact on the spread of tuberculosis through the accumulation of sources of infection due to the low effectiveness of treatment.

To date, against the backdrop of a global epidemic of multiple or extensive drug resistance of tuberculosis, it is necessary both to optimize the diagnosis of resistant forms of tuberculosis and the early administration of a course of controlled chemotherapy, selected based on the drug sensitivity of the pathogen, as well as the inclusion in the course of chemotherapy of new anti-TB drugs that are effective against drug-resistant form x of tuberculosis [1,2,3] .

Materials and methods of research: the data of examination of 84 patients with drug-resistant forms of tuberculosis were analyzed . The age of the patients varied from 19 to 68 years, the mean age was 51.4 years . At men the disease occurred 1.6 times more, and 77.0 % of patients were over the age of 50 years.

Results and discussion: The effectiveness of treatment depends on adequate anti-tuberculosis therapy, pathogenetic therapy, as well as compliance with sanitary-epidemiological and rehabilitation measures. The effectiveness of bacteriological research methods was studied (actoroscopy, MGM , sowing methods) .

A comparative analysis revealed that the sensitivity of the method is higher for the molecular genetic method - 79.5 ± 8.6 % of cases, and the seeding method is more specific and amounted to - 29.7 ± 27.7 % .

Sputum abacillation after 1 month was registered in 59 (70.24%), after 2 months - 16 (19.05%), after 3 months - 4 (0.5 %), after 4 months - in 3 (0.36 %), after 5 months - in 1 (0.12%) and after 6 months - in 1 (0.12%) cases. Clinical symptoms disappeared after 1-5 months.

Thus, in comparative analyzes of bacteriological methods studies have found that molecular genetic methods are more sensitive than seeding methods. With adequate use of anti-tuberculosis therapy, the terms of sputum abacillation after 3 months were - in 91,87 % of cases.

References:

1. Avetisyan A.O., Grishko A.N. About Yuri Mikhailovich Repin. Medical Alliance. 2016; #1: 6–8.
2. Balasanyants G.S. The development of the epidemic process in tuberculosis: the influence of external and internal factors. Infection and immunity. Specialist. release. 2014: 13–17
3. . Belyaeva E.N., Dyakova M.E., Esmedlyaeva D.S., Nazarenko M.M., Sapozhnikova N.V., Starshinova A.A. Markers of the inflammatory response in pulmonary tuberculosis patients with Mycobacterium tuberculosis drug resistance. Journal of Infectology. 2017; 9(4): 31–37

